

Low-cost WS₂ Photodetector on Water-Soluble Paper for Transient Electronics

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Abstract

The rapid development of technology has led to a significant increase in production of electronic devices. However, this growth also brings forth the challenge of electronic waste (e-waste). To overcome this challenge, transient electronics with the capability of disintegrating or disappearing after operation have attracted widespread attention in recent years. Controlled disintegration of such systems without the need for harsh solvents and long periods of time is a step towards realizing green and sustainable electronics. Here we demonstrate a dissolvable eco-friendly flexible photodetector using an abraded WS₂ on a water-soluble paper substrate. The whole device can physically disappear in water in ~ 60 s and the electronic materials can be recovered by vacuum filtration. The device shows a photoresponsivity of $\sim 176 \mu\text{A W}^{-1}$ under ambient conditions.

Keywords: transient electronics, paper electronics; photodetector; van der Waals materials, tungsten disulfide

1. INTRODUCTION

With the accelerated development of electronics, the production of devices is rapidly escalating worldwide leading to significant amounts of electronic waste that often cannot be efficiently recycled.¹⁻³ Even if the degradation of standard electronic components does occur, it often results in the release of toxic materials posing significant risks to living organisms and the environment.⁴

This big problem motivated researchers and industries to not only improve recycling methods but also to create electronics with lower environmental footprint upon end of use. Biodegradable electronics that can partially or completely degrade in nature have emerged as an essential solution to reduce environmental burdens.⁵ Although long-term operation is a feature of traditional electronics, biodegradable devices can potentially offer great benefits to temporary biomedical implants, green environmental electronics and secure hardware. Till now, a wide range of biodegradable substrates (such as paper, silk, synthetic polymers, etc.) have been reported.⁶⁻⁸ Partially degradable inorganic transistors on a silk substrate proposed the concept of transitional electronics for the first time.⁹ Despite their excellent degradation capability and performance, silk electronics are highly susceptible to water and solvents. Several studies have reported depositing organic semiconductors on paper and polymeric substrates. The degradation time of these materials can be adjusted from a few days to several years, depending on specific applications. In recent studies, silicon nanomembranes dissolve in physiological environments at a rate of a few nanometers to more than 100 nm per day, depending on the types of aqueous solutions.¹⁰⁻¹⁴ However, even though they are flexible and degradable, the performance of such devices falls behind the requirements of many electronics applications.

Apart from biodegradable electronics, there are other applications that require very fast degradation after use. Transient electronics are an emerging class of functional electronic

devices to operate over a short time and predefined duration of time, varying from a few minutes to days, without need for harsh solvents.^{15–17} They are designed to disintegrate, either partially or completely, through electrochemical, mechanical, or chemical reactions when no longer needed.^{16,18–20} For instance, temporary implantable biomedical devices are designed to degrade in the body and do not require secondary surgery to extract the device.^{21–23} The unique property of transient electronics to break down into harmless substances when triggered by environmental factors such as moisture, light, or temperature, initiate the way for research areas like eco-friendly electronics, implantable biomedical devices, hardware security, and environmental sensors.^{24–28} These controlled degradable devices are promising solutions for eco-friendly and sustainable electronics.

In this study, we report the first demonstration of a WS₂ transient photodetector on water-soluble paper based on the direct abrasion of photoactive material and electrode. While transient electronics on water-soluble substrates are not new, previous research have focused on organic or polymeric active materials with limited environmental stability and spectral tunability. Here, the WS₂ is selected as a photoactive material due to its high optical absorption in the visible range, excellent photoconductive properties. Graphite is chosen as the electrode material for its high electrical conductivity and compatibility with paper-based substrates, while also offering an eco-friendly alternative to metal electrodes, aligning with the sustainability goal of this work. By integration of these materials on a water-soluble paper substrate, we enable a high-performance, and eco-friendly photodetector along with the possibility of recycling the materials. The device demonstrates high and reproducible photoresponse. The significant improvement in photoresponse has been achieved by increasing incident light power and by applying a high bias voltage. Moreover, we show that the device can be completely dissolved in water in 60 s and the electronic materials (electrodes and semiconductor channel) can be recovered by vacuum filtering. This capability paves the way for future research exploring the

reusability of recovered materials, potentially enhancing the sustainability of transient electronics. Taking advantage of these superior properties, developing paper-based transient photodetectors seems to be not only a cost-effective solution but also offers environmentally friendly and disposable functionalities.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: WS₂ Photodetector on water-soluble paper. (a) Process sequence of paper-based photodetector device fabrication by abrasion of WS₂ powder and drawing the electrodes using a 9B graphite pencil. (b) A photograph of the fabricated WS₂ photodetector device, (c) Cross-sectional SEM images of WS₂ flakes deposited on water-soluble paper, illustrating the integration of WS₂ with graphite electrodes.

Figure 1(a) shows the preparation process of the soluble WS₂ photodetector. The device fabrication begins with printing of the outline using an office printer (Brother MFCL5700DN) on soluble paper (Jaboneko, 0.55 g cm⁻³) which is made of sodium methyl carboxyl cellulose and wood pulp. Then, the channel area is delimited by using Nitto tape (SPV 224) to create stencils and control the geometry of the deposited films. WS₂ powder (0.6 μm APS Micronized, HAGEN Automation,) is rubbed against the unmasked surface of the paper with a cotton swab.

To verify the quality of the film, a handheld multimeter is used, and the rubbing process is repeated until a resistance between two probes separated by $\sim 1\text{--}2$ mm reaches a range of $\sim 1\text{--}5$ M Ω . Following this, the masking tape is removed, and the graphite electrodes are drawn with 9B pencil (Monolith, 20409) onto WS₂ and the printed electrode outline. The completed WS₂ photodetector device is shown in Figure 1(b), demonstrating the effective integration of WS₂ on water-soluble paper and confirming the viability of the production technique.

A cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image demonstrates a microscopic view of the WS₂ flakes formed on the water-soluble paper and the integration of the graphite electrodes into the device (Figure 1c). The graphite electrode and WS₂ film can be distinguished due to their difference in material properties under SEM analysis. As can be seen, the WS₂ nanosheets form a network of flakes interconnected through junctions.^{29,30} Additionally, we analyzed the thickness of the WS₂ flakes forming the film finding the modal value of 116 ± 5 nm but exhibiting a significant thickness variation throughout the film, due to the fibrous structure of the paper (Figure S1)

Figure 2: Photoresponse characteristics of the WS₂ photodetector on water-soluble paper. (a) Time-resolved photocurrent response under periodic illumination switching at 5 V bias voltage (the red line marks the baseline of the spectrum) (b) Photocurrent vs. time curve (after subtraction of the baseline) under different incident light intensities at 5V bias voltage, (c) Photocurrent (left) and responsivity (right) as functions of light power density. Measurements are taken at a bias of 5 V and under 660 nm light illumination. The device features a channel width of approximately 0.8 mm and a length of 8.8 mm.

The photodetection performance of the fabricated WS₂ device is studied using a homebuilt probe station with a source-measure unit (Keithley 2450) under dark and light illumination of an external 660 nm wavelength LED (Thorlabs fiber-coupled LEDs).³¹ Figure 2a shows the photocurrent-time characteristics of the device while the illumination is switched periodically ON and OFF at a fixed power density of 1.63 mW cm⁻² (at 5 V bias). The current demonstrates an increase upon illumination and returns to the initial dark current value when the light source is turned off, the device exhibits consistent and reversible switching behavior under 125 on/off cycles (Figure S2).

The transient photoresponse under excitation of different incident power intensities (from 0.18 mW cm⁻² to 1.63 mW cm⁻²), as shown in Figure 2b, shows a gradual increase of photocurrent with the increment of incident power (the baseline has been subtracted to enable quantitative comparison). As the intensity of the incident light increases, more photons interact with the WS₂ film, generating an increased number of electron-hole pairs. This increased generation of charge carriers allows more charge carriers to contribute to the current, resulting in a higher photoresponse³². Additionally, by increasing the excitation power, the response time becomes shorter due to faster charge carrier generation and recombination (Figure S3).^{33,34}

Figure 2c shows the extracted photocurrent and responsivity values (obtained from Figure 2b) as a function of the incident light power. At high illumination power, an increase in photocurrent is observed. To quantify this increase, the photocurrent for different incident power regimes is plotted (Figure S4) and fitted by the power-law

$$I_{PC} = A \times P^\alpha$$

where I_{PC} is the photocurrent and A as well as α are fitting parameters. The photocurrent follows a sub-linear trend with $\alpha \approx 0.5 \pm 0.04$ under lower incident power (< 1 mW/cm²), due to photogating effects (Figure S4a).^{35,36} By increasing the light power (>1 mW/cm²) the photocurrent follows a transition from sublinear to strong superlinearity with $\alpha \approx 1.37 \pm 0.06$,

which is unusual for homogeneous 2D materials. The photocurrent transition from sublinear to strong superlinearity in the WS₂ photodetector can be attributed to various mechanisms such as the bolometric effect and photothermoelectric effect. Photothermoelectric and bolometric currents both arise from thermal mechanisms. The difference between them is that a thermoelectric current occurs due to the temperature gradient induced by light absorption, while a bolometric effect results from the change in the global temperature of the material under bias, which alters the current. These combined effects can significantly enhance the photocurrent, resulting in a superlinear behavior indicates photoconductive effect (Figure S4b).^{37–39} Note that, increasing light power is related with a decrease in responsivity due to the power dependence of I_{PC} ($R=I_{PC}/P$, P is the light power).

Figure 3: Voltage dependence of photocurrent generation in WS₂ photodetectors. (a) Photocurrent response ON-OFF behavior of the photodetector under different bias voltages. (b) Voltage-dependent photocurrent and responsivity of the device at fixed power of 0.7mW. NOTE: Measurements are taken at a wavelength of 660 nm.

We further studied the response of the device to different bias voltages at a fixed wavelength (660 nm). The current is dramatically increased upon light on and drops after the light is switched off, which is also verified with current-time characteristics in Figure S5 under different light power. The responsivity and photocurrent are compared at fixed light power intensity of 1.63 mW cm⁻² (660 nm) under different biases (Figure 3b). Both photocurrent and

responsivity increase gradually as the applied voltage increases, from ~ 0.21 nA and $\sim 1.68 \mu\text{AW}^{-1}$, reaching ~ 22 nA and $\sim 176 \mu\text{AW}^{-1}$ respectively.

The photoresponse of the paper-based photodetector is further examined under various wavelengths, ranging from 470 nm to 740 nm, at constant intensity of 0.70 mWcm^{-2} (Figure S6). The fabricated device exhibits a good broad spectral response from 470nm to 740nm with the peak sensitivity located at 660nm. This behavior can be attributed to the intrinsic optical absorption properties of WS_2 . Additionally, the responsivity increases with the wavelength and exhibits a higher response ($83 \mu\text{AW}^{-1}$) under the illumination of a 660 nm monochromatic light.

To evaluate the mechanical durability of the WS_2 photodetector, the electrical response is measured under different applied strains. The I-V characteristics under different strain levels (0%–0.44%) are shown in Figure S7. The results demonstrate a consistent and nearly linear behavior across all strain conditions, indicating that the electrical contacts remain stable under deformation, and the charge transport within the device is preserved. Furthermore, gauge factor (GF) is extracted from the relative resistance change ($\Delta R/R_0$) as a function of strain, resulting in values of 32.7 and 31.9 for bias voltages of -5V and +5V, respectively. These values indicate that the device can effectively maintain its performance under mechanical deformations.

Figure 4: Recycling of WS₂ photodetector. (a) Images of the dissolving process steps of paper-based WS₂ photodetector in DI water. (b) Vacuum filtering process of the dissolved device, illustrating the recovered materials.

To demonstrate the degradability of the fabricated photodetector, the device is placed into de-ionized (DI) water at room temperature. Figure 4a shows a series of captured images demonstrating the dissolving process. The process consists of three steps: water absorption, disintegration and dissolution. In the first step, the device immediately absorbs the water and subsequently the substrate starts to disintegrate. In 60 seconds, the device substrate disappears while the other elements of the device get suspended in the water. Moreover, the materials used for device fabrication are collected by using a vacuum filtration method based on cellulose filter paper (prat dumas, 47 mm) with 0.20 μm pore size (Figure 4b). Since WS₂ is chemically stable in water and does not dissolve under ambient conditions, it remains suspended along with other non-soluble components after the substrate disintegrates. This is because WS₂ has a layered structure, where tungsten (W) atoms are covalently bonded to sulfur (S) atoms, making it resistant to interaction with water molecules due to its high bond energy and the hydrophobic nature of its sulfur-terminated surfaces.^{40,41} Therefore, the vacuum filtration process efficiently separates these materials from the solution, enabling their recovery for potential reuse. We

address the reader to a video that shows the overall dissolving process (see Video S1 in Supplementary information).

Furthermore, we investigate whether the recovered materials remain unaltered by the recycling process, opening the door for reusing them in the future. Raman spectroscopy measurements are taken to identify the recovered materials' properties (laser wavelength of 532 nm). The Raman spectra of WS₂ on soluble and filter paper are shown in Figure S8. Abraded WS₂ on soluble paper exhibits characteristic modes E_{2g}^1 and A_{1g} appearing at 346 and 419 cm⁻¹ respectively. These peaks serve as spectral fingerprints, confirming the presence of WS₂ on paper. The collected Raman spectrum from filter paper provides two significant outcomes to comprehensively understand the material after the dissolution process. Spectrum 1 obtained from large bulk area (Figure S8-b) distinctly exhibits the characteristic WS₂ Raman peaks. On the other hand, spectrum 2 demonstrates a mix of WS₂ and graphite. These results are also consistent with the Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX) results. The EDX spectrum indicates the presence of elements W and S in the films, which confirms the presence of WS₂ before and after filtration (Figure S9).

3. CONCLUSION

In summary, we successfully demonstrated a flexible, cost-effective transient photodetector consisting of abraded WS₂ as an active channel, pencil-drawing graphite as electrodes, and water-soluble paper as the device substrate. The as-fabricated devices exhibit reversible response upon light illumination cycles. Moreover, the responsivity can be improved by applying higher biasing voltage, achieving a maximum of 176 μA W⁻¹ at a voltage of 45 V. Finally, we demonstrated that the detector can be fully dissolved in water within a minute.

This work demonstrates the potential of soluble WS₂ transient photodetectors, offering a valuable step towards addressing the growing challenge of electronic waste. Overall, we believe

that our findings greatly expand new possibilities for electronic applications, not only reducing their cost but also minimizing e-waste to address global environmental concerns. Furthermore, our work emphasizes on the economic contribution of transient technologies by recovering materials that, upon might be re-used in other processes or devices.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interests.

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